

Effect of climate change on Marginal farmers in Hyderabad Karnataka: A Social Study

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ABSTRACT:

Increasing carbon dioxide concentrations in the atmosphere, the expansion of available areas for tropical and subtropical crop production, two crop cultivation, and crop fertility as a result of fertilization are positive effects of global warming. The weather affects every aspect of our lives, from our food sources to our transportation infrastructure, what clothes we wear, where we go on holidays. It has a huge impact on our livelihood, our health and our future. Weather is a long-term model of weather conditions at any given location. Mixed methods approach including quantitative and qualitative data were employed. Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire through a household survey during September and October 2020. The study respondents were 50 Marginal farmers in the flood-prone areas of Hyderabad Karnataka. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, coefficient of correlation and stepwise regression. This will have a major impact on agricultural production. Climatic extremes have led to a high rate of land degradation, resulting in increased soil erosion and lack of nutrients. This study has a major impact on farmers, agricultural production. Climatic extremes have led to a high rate of land degradation, resulting in increased soil erosion and lack of nutrients.

Keywords: Climate Change, Marginal Farmers, Floods, Impact, crop Production.

Introduction

Climate is changing rapidly, affecting many areas throughout the globe and it is emerging as a major threat to sustainable development. Globally, an unparalleled increase in greenhouse emissions promotes climate change impacts. Thus, the consequences of climate change affect the food security and agriculture livelihoods of large sections of the urban and rural populations globally. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change¹. Climate change has had a major impact on the farmers of Hyderabad Karnataka, generally in terms of farmers'

7.8 M land holdings of 1.55 ha average area. The small and marginal holdings account 76% of the total holdings in the state which occupy about 40% of the operated area (Agricultural Census 2010-11). Of the total cultivated area, the net irrigated area is about 4.09 M hectares (33%) and the net rainfed cultivated area is about 6.41 M hectares in the state. The Karnataka state has the second largest rain-fed agriculture area after Rajasthan. As, about 55% of total food grain and 74% of oilseeds production come from rain-fed agriculture in Karnataka, the rain-fed agriculture plays an important role in total food grain production in the state. The state has three cropping seasons namely i) Kharif (6.92 Mha), ii) Rabi (3.03Mha), iii) Summer (0.59Mha). Among the agricultural crops cereals (49%), pulses (24%), oilseeds (15%), cotton (6%), sugarcane (5%), tobacco (1%) occupy major area in the state. About 2.1Mha (17%) of the cultivated area is occupied by different horticultural crops such as Mango, Banana, Pomegranate, Papaya, Vegetables, Plantation crops like Coconut, Arecanut, Coffee, Cardamom and Pepper.²

agricultural activities and in the social, economic, modern and climate change aspects of agriculture, the effects of climate change have many effects on farmers. The Indian subcontinent is particularly vulnerable to major earthquakes, hurricanes, floods, erosion, landslides and shrubs. Extreme natural hazards, especially floods and floods, are emerging. A major concern in the plains of Karnataka. These are becoming more frequent nowadays and there are always increasing lives and climate change and natural disasters. Has devastating effects on the economy; They are huge. Human social and economic losses and significant disruptions, economic development of a region or country, natural disasters, crops and livestock sink, some storms and droughts, water supply is contaminated and wells fail when rainfall fails. However, the recent flood has hit the Karnataka region of Hyderabad, especially for small and marginal farmers, landless laborers, land-poor farmers, socially backward classes and peasant women. In recent times, the impact of flooding on agricultural activities has been analyzed and the effects of farmers' climate change model, objectives and agricultural activities have been investigated. Over the past few years, the rate of flooding has significantly increased

over the flood situation and farmers' economic conditions, which have an impact on the farmer's farming life.

In most developing countries, smallholder farmers have insufficient opportunities to learn about new technologies and improved agricultural methods (Tsafack et al, 2015). This is because agricultural extension services are unable to develop low-cost sustainable approaches to providing information and services. Speranza et al, (2009) portrays the importance of extension services in agriculture. It ensures the transmission of innovations from research institutions, build farmer's capacities and enable them share their experiences. With climate change and other environmental stressors, the extension approaches, the methods adopted and the type of information communicated needs to be improved upon.³

Review of literature

The purpose of this paper is to consider the climatic variables and evaluate the role of non-climatic factors that delicately influence agriculture. This study has come across various adaptation strategies such as modification in cultivation practices such as shifting planting dates, water-saving techniques and strategic nutrient management. Meanwhile, we are trying to forget the ground reality that a majority of the farmers are not aware of climate-resilient production technologies. However, farmers modify themselves in this climate change scenario for sustainable production. The practice of these adaptation strategies helps to reduce vulnerability to improve their "socio-economic status" and the "quality of life".⁴

effectively communicate climate-related information to farmers due to their low competency, limited numbers and poor access to information. Inaccessible sectors have low innovation adoption rates because they have less contact with extension agents. As such, in increasing the number of extension workers, it is essential to move extension from a top-down program to a program that uses a co-production approach and lay emphasis on-farm demonstration. However, it necessitates new competencies and roles.³

The temporal analysis of rainfall and temperature, the related data on average maximum and minimum temperatures and average rainfall were collected for the period 2001-2008 from the official records of the district agricultural department, Hamirpur. The analysis period was taken for five years i.e. 2004-2008 with the baseline year as the average of three years i.e. 2001-2003 for temperature and rainfall. Based on the available information, year-wise average change of maximum and minimum temperature, change in temperature difference and impact of temperature fluctuation on rainfall pattern were drawn, the predominant situation was characterized by clay (Mar) and clay loam (Kabar) soil, rainfed and mono-cropping situation which occupied about 60 per cent of the total area. Under this situation, major cropping sequences were kharif fallow-lentil + linseed and mixed cropping of chickpea + linseed in that order of acreage. The second important situation which shared 20 per cent of the area was characterized by clay loam (Kabar) and Loam (Parwa) soils with partially irrigated condition and monocropped situation.⁵

The pre tested structured schedules were used to collect primary data of 100 households in 10 villages of Upper Krishna Project area of Karnataka for the farming season 2009– 10 and 2010-11. 20 years monthly meteorological data of temperature and rainfall of CADA, agro-meteorological station Bheemarayangudi were used for analysis. The study on impact of disaster/flood revealed that 59 per cent of the respondents lost their crops, while 31 per cent were lost complete farm activities. In the later period land was occupied by unwanted weeds. The local people reported that the invasion was much noticed in last 2-3 years even though they tried to remove the weed in time.⁶

Objective

1. To study the climate change effect on farmers
2. To analyze the cropping pattern, Socioeconomic agriculture of farmers
3. To identify the contributory factors for farmers climate change
4. To review the relief and rehabilitation measures of the farmers

Hypotheses

1. Climate change has influenced on farmers social life.
2. Government and resettlement measures have helped farmers' climate change family members.

Methods

The Hyderabad-Karnataka region comprises of Bidar, Kalaburagi, Yadgir, Raichur, Koppala, Bellary and districts. The Hyderabad-Karnataka region is the second-largest arid region in India. The study was conducted in Hyderabad Karnataka region is mainly selected for study purposively as it recorded a high rainfall coming and changes of farmer's condition. The study is based on primary source of questionnaire information and data. Primary data including farmers season and crop, Hyderabad-Karnataka region of Karnataka state, India covers the realm of 44,145 sq.km. Which accounts for 23.02% of the entire geographical region of the Karnataka state. The region covers six major districts of Karnataka state, namely, Ballary, Koppala, Raichur, Kalaburagi, Yadgir and Bidar. This region is characterized by dryness for the major a part of the year and a very hot summer. The region receives rainfall both from southwest and northeast monsoon. However, the mean rainfall within the region is extremely scant at 692mm in an exceedingly year. The geographical location of the study area is presented.⁴

Figure 1. Mapshowing the Study Area

in **Figure 1**. The study was based on a cross-sectional survey data from Marginal farming households across six districts of Bidar, Kalaburagi, Yadgir, Raichur, Koppala, Ballary. A mixed-mode study design including both quantitative survey and qualitative methods such as focus group discussions, key informant interviews, and field observations were employed. The household survey was employed through one-on-one interviews and data regarding farmers' perception, socioeconomic attributes of the farmers were collected. Data gathered using the qualitative methods were utilized to prepare the survey instrument and also to support the study findings.

Sampling, data collection and analysis, Results

Personal information of marginal farmers are shown in Table 1. The respondent of the study area

Frequencies variables=gender age education income house csantiles=4, percentiles=50.0, statistics=stddev mean, format=limit (10), order=analysis.

Socio-economic characteristics of smallholder farmers are shown in

Table 1. Findings show that most of the respondents of the study area were middle-aged (43 per cent). The majority (36 per cent) of the respondents did not attend any formal schooling. A 71 per cent of respondents had Marginal household size and 60 per cent had 0.22ha to 0.46 ha of land holdings with an average value of 0.485 ha.

S no:		Gender of the participants	Age of the participants	Educational Qualification	How many per year your Income	Ownership of house	Do you have A CSA (Community Supported Agriculture) program
N	Valid	50	50	50	50	50	50
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.0600	2.5200	1.1400	1.2800	1.4800	2.0000
Std. Deviation		.23990	.93110	.35051	.45356	.70682	.00000
Percentiles	25	1.0000	2.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	2.0000
	50	1.0000	2.5000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	2.0000
	75	1.0000	3.0000	1.0000	2.0000	2.0000	2.0000

Table 1 personal information of the respondents(N=50).

Descriptive variables of the study were socio-economic Characteristics of minor farmers, gender, age, Education, Per year your Income, Owen ship of house Community Supported Agriculture program (CSA)access to information Basic and training experience. The explanatory variables were measured accordingly. To raw data by developing and using appropriate quantities In addition, multiple linear regression and stepwise regression was used to determine the factors affecting marginal farmers' perception of climate change impact on crop production.

How do you get information on climate change forecastles

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Radio/TV	19	38.0	38.0	38.0
	Word of Mouth	31	62.0	62.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 Information to climate change

Data in table 2 showed that majority of the respondents (62 percent) perceived that climate change information on word to mouth and Respondents information about the (38 percent) Radio/tv. Climate change is manly information farmer to farmer mouth taken.

		Types of soil	Land for Agricultural Use	Do you do crop-sharing farming	The condition of the farmer when the flood comes	Do you have crop insurance	Which crop will most likely grow in black soil	Monsoon impact diseases	How many Natural Disasters you have handled during your service period	Types of Crops
N	Valid	50	50	50	50	13	50	50	50	50
	Missing	0	0	0	0	37	0	0	0	0
Std. Deviation		.50346	1.00285	.49031	1.38873	.43853	.62629	.78246	.88156	1.01015
Variance		.253	1.006	.240	1.929	.192	.392	.612	.777	1.020
Range		1.00	2.00	1.00	3.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00

Table 3. Range order of impact of climate change as perceived by the respondents(n=50)

Frequencies

variables=types_soilland_agriculturecrop_farfarmer_floodcrop_insuranceblack_soil,monsoon_impactn_disasters crops, statistics=stddev variance range order=analysis.

Increased intensity of floods was found as most important impact with stddev 1.39 (R - 3)as per respondents. Influenced type of crop stddev 1.02 and Range (3) was mainly important impact of climate change on marginal farmers.

		Age of the participants	How many per year your Income	Do you do crop-sharing farming	Do you have A CSA (Community Supported Agriculture) program
Age of the participants	Pearson Correlation	1	.421**	-.755**	-.318*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002	.000	.024
	N	50	50	50	50
How many per year your Income	Pearson Correlation	.421**	1	.062	-.089
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002		.667	.538
	N	50	50	50	50
Do you do crop-sharing farming	Pearson Correlation	-.755**	.062	1	.261
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.667		.067
	N	50	50	50	50
Do you have A CSA (Community Supported Agriculture) program	Pearson Correlation	-.318*	-.089	.261	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024	.538	.067	
	N	50	50	50	50

Table 4. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Participants' age is agricultural experience, access to information sources and training, Experience has a significant and positive relationship with a small holder. It reveals how much of your income you earn per year in crop allocation. Farmers' community-supported agricultural perception of climate change affects crop production. Step-by-step multiple regression analysis, Stepwise multiple regression analysis was employed to understand, The individual contribution of the explanatory variable to the variance of marginal farmers' perceptions of the impact of climate change on crop production.

Discussion

Mainly respondents in the study area Climate change is a reality. Indian agriculture is likely to suffer losses due to intensity, incidental weather and receded irrigation availability. Climate change proposes a promising hazard to tenable development.⁷ Large farmers were study reveals the different sources of uncertainty among farmers about climate change, farmers' decision-making ability, and economic performance under uncertain situations. Component-wise

analysis, decision-making capacity, and financial performance were signifying- scanty better in big farmers when compare with small and marginal farmers.⁸ Climate Changes in seasons and season length of a region are driven by shifts in the intensity of sunlight reaching earth's surface (insolation), latitude, con- tangential and marine climate, wind direction, and local geographical features. Since change in season length is an indicator, as well as an effect, of climate change and is less studied, the objective of this study was set to investigate the variability of future season length to some of the uncertainties such as the choice of climate scenario, predictors, definition of seasons and number of seasons.⁹ The impact of climate change on species and local landraces, declining productivity, outbreak of pests and diseases, rapid encroachment by invasive species and emergence of human diseases.⁶

Conclusion

It is obvious that there are Marginal land farmers, The study area perceives the severe impacts of climate change on crop production. There really are some kind of programs in it- U.S. Global Change Research Program. USDA Weather Hubs. Climate Program Office, NOAA. Global Change Master Directory, NASA. ARS National Climate Change, Soil and Emissions Program. Forces to resolve Providing appropriate solutions to farmers. Short farmers experience in the study area, and insect infestation, lack of water. Improvement of maximum growing arsons requires some immediate relief, research on smallholder farmers adapting to climate change. Bringing in some relevant findings and recommendations for the study. Moreover, the government may take initiatives to provide some logistic Supports such as pesticide sprayers, easy access to electricity and subsidy. Shallow or deep tube wells in the study area. Socio-economic characteristics. General farming, farming experience and training experience. There have been major factors affecting farmers 'perception of climate change Effects. So, programs that focus on these aspects are probably. Increases farmers 'perception and adaptability to climate change Effects. Finally, there is a need for an integrated approach, including government and both, to significantly address supplier solutions.

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